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ABSTRACT

The electron gun to be built and tested within ARIES WP16 is designed for integration into an electron lens for space-charge compensation in the heavy ion synchrotron SIS18. In order to verify the suitability of the gun design for this purpose, electron beam dynamics simulations have been performed with special focus on extraction and transport of the electron beam into the interaction region, where the requirements on the electron beam properties for space-charge compensation are defined. In this report, an overview over the layout of the electron lens is given and results of the electron beam dynamics simulations are presented

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

The main objective of WP16 is the construction and testing of an electron gun for integration into an electron lens for space-charge compensation. The design of the gun needs to be verified against the corresponding requirements. This report presents results of beam dynamics simulations performed to validate the gun design. It marks the completion of task 16.2, which is dedicated to the system integration of the electron gun.

The main conclusion from the simulation studies is that the design of the electron gun developed within task 16.3 satisfies all requirements set by the space-charge compensation electron lens.

Due to technical difficulties with the simulation tool, the scope of the electron beam dynamics simulations had to be reduced compared to the original plans. However, the reduced scope is sufficient for the verification of the gun design.

1. Introduction

ARIES WP16, running under the name “Intense RF Electron Beams (IRME)”, is a JRA aiming at the construction and testing of a RF modulated electron gun to be used in electron lenses for compensation of space-charge in bunched hadron beams. While task 16.3 is concerned with the construction of gun and modulator and task 16.4 with the testing, task 16.2 is actually supposed to provide the boundary conditions for and requirements on the electron gun as demanded by the design of an electron lens for a real accelerator.

This purpose is served by the heavy ion synchrotron SIS18 at GSI, representing a larger class of hadron circular accelerators whose intensity is limited by the transverse space-charge tune spread at injection. GSI has started the development of a prototype electron lens for space-charge compensation in SIS18, the ultimate goal being to develop a generic tool for increasing intensities in the FAIR facility. While the complete design of this lens is outside the scope of WP16, the intended compensation scheme defines the main parameters of the electron gun. In particular, a peak current of 10 A is required, modulated at frequencies in the range of 400 kHz to 1 MHz with a bandwidth of about 10 MHz. The IRME electron gun will employ a novel modulation concept, modulating the beam by a grid between cathode and anode. This is necessary to guarantee a stable transverse beam profile under the modulation, and to minimize the power requirements on the modulator. Under these conditions, an extraction voltage of 30 kV is needed to reach the desired peak current. The magnetic system of the electron lens, consisting of solenoids and toroids, provides the necessary longitudinal magnetic field of 0.6 T for transverse confinement of the intense electron beam.

One important step in the design of the IRME electron gun is the verification of the properties of the electron beam created by the gun throughout the whole lens, but in particular in the interaction region, where the electron beam overlaps the positively charged ion beam, creating a focusing force counteracting the defocusing action of the repulsive force created by the ion beam’s space-charge. Such a verification requires simulations of extraction and transport of the electron beam, including the electron beam’s own space-charge. This contribution gives an overview of the electron lens layout, putting special emphasis on the design of the electron gun. Also, the results of the electron beam

dynamics simulations are presented. All simulations were performed using the 3D CST STUDIO software.

2. Design Overview of the Electron Lens Device

The electron lens is comprised of the magnetic system, consisting of solenoids and toroids to guide the electron beam onto the ion beam path in order to create the desired interaction, the electron gun to generate the electron beam, and a collector, which serves as a disposal area for the electrons at the end. The 3D design of the electron lens is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of the electron lens. Magnetic system of the lens consists of solenoids and toroids.

Figure 2. Cross sectional view of the electron lens. It shows the magnetic components, and their geometrical arrangements.

The total length of the device is about 8 meters and the interaction region, where the electron beam will be matched onto the ion beam path, is 3.36 m long. Coil geometrical arrangements and iron casing are shown in Figure 2. The magnetic system has been designed for a maximum longitudinal field of 0.6 T and has been presented in more detail in the MS55 milestone report [1].

For the layout of the electron lens and of its main components, especially electron gun and collector, electron beam dynamics simulations are an important design tool. In this context, beam dynamics simulations involve beam current extraction, beam acceleration, transport, and beam deceleration, all taking into account the space-charge of the intense electron beam, as well as the simulation of the disposal in the collector, where secondary electron emission processes are very important. Simulating those effects consistently is a formidable task, given the various physical processes to be considered, the large overall scale of the system and the enormous scale differences present in the problem. In particular, the scale for the required resolution is set by the structure of the electron gun with its grid structures on a mm-scale and a distance of 3 mm between cathode and grid. Yet, the total length to be covered in simulations extends over several meters. This explains the complexity of simulating the full electron beam dynamics for the whole device.

While the original plan for task 16.2 involved a simulation of the electron beam dynamics for the complete electron lens including space-charge effects, this plan had to be abandoned due to the complexity of the task and serious problems with the simulation software leading to unphysical results under certain conditions.

Instead, the simulation of the system was divided into several subsections: the beam extraction from the electron gun, the beam transport through the first straight and first bending section, the beam transport in the main solenoid, and the beam transport through the last bending section followed by beam disposal in the collector.

In this report the focus is set on the results for the simulation of the extraction from the electron gun, the beam transport through the first straight and bending section, and transport through the main solenoid. This reduction of the scope is justified, since the major objective of WP16 as a JRA is the construction and testing of an RF modulated electron gun. The requirements on this electron gun, however, do not depend on the beam dynamics in the last part of the electron lens, which we were not able to complete due to the serious computational issues described above. They are, of course, important for the design of the whole electron lens, but this is outside the scope of WP16. The results of the extraction and transport simulations will be presented in the following sections.

3. Electron Gun Design

3.1 REQUIREMENTS

The electron lens considered in this report is designed to reduce the space-charge forces within a bunched hadron beam circulating in a synchrotron. In synchrotrons, space-charge always acts as a distributed defocussing force [2]. Its strength is characterized by the incoherent space-charge tune spread. An electron lens can be used to reduce the space-charge tune spread by providing a counter-acting focusing force. For the heavy ion synchrotron SIS18, the aim is to reduce the vertical space-charge tune spread from 0.5 to 0.3. Since electron lenses are necessarily localized devices, several electron lenses have to be installed around the ring in order to retain enough symmetry in the synchrotron. Assuming an interaction region of $N_e L_e = 22$ m, a peak electron current of $I_{e,max} = 10$ A is required and this has to be provided by the electron gun. Besides the requirement on peak current, the electron beam needs to be modulated in time to follow the longitudinal current profile of the bunched beam, which changes during a complete SIS18 cycle. Furthermore, the transverse profile has an influence on the space-charge compensation. For this reason, two compensation schemes are under investigation: A Gaussian beam distribution that exactly matches the transvers ion beam profile, as well as a homogeneous beam distribution covering the cross-section of the ion beam. For the design of the IRME gun, it was decided to study the more challenging case of a Gaussian distribution.

The requirements on the electron beam discussed before can be summarized as follows:

- maximum current of 10 A
- Gaussian profile (or homogeneous profile) with elliptical shape in the x-y plane
- RF modulation to create a predefined longitudinal bunch profile

More details on the electron gun requirements can be found in MS53 [3].

3.2 CONCEPTUAL DESIGN – SIMULATION OF ELECTRON BEAM EMISSION

In order to generate a Gaussian beam, a Gaussian cathode shape was chosen. For the beam modulation there are several options: anode modulation, the modulation of the control electrode, and grid modulation. The latter was found to be the only suitable modulation option for the design of the IRME gun. To study extraction, beam suppression, as well as the transport properties of the solenoids, a model of the electron gun was implemented in CST Particle Studio (CST-PS). Before performing detailed simulations on the grid design, the code was benchmarked with TRAK for a tested gun design by A. Pikin (BNL). The results of CST-PS were comparable to TRAK concerning maximum extracted current and perveance, with only minor changes appearing for the centre ($r = 0$) of the current density profile. In order to resolve the small distance between cathode and grid of 3 mm, high resolutions and therefore long simulation times were required.

For the simulations in CST-PS, space-charge limited emission is chosen as tracking emission model. Physically, the space-charge limited emission can be understood as a suppression of the potential

between two planar electrodes by a cloud of charges. In the numerical model, space-charge limited emission is derived from the one-dimensional Child-Langmuir model [4]. Figure 3 shows a model of the electron gun in CST-PS, as well as results for the beam distribution and the normalized transverse current density profile at the exit of the gun ($z = 170$ mm).

Figure 3. Model of the electron gun set-up in CST-PS (top), electron beam distribution (bottom, left) and normalized current density distribution of the extracted beam (bottom, right) at the exit of the gun.

For the given geometry and an anode potential of 30 kV, an extracted current of 10.4 A is predicted. Since the ion beam in the synchrotron has an elliptical shape, the simulation model was also used to study beam profile shaping by a quadrupole field. Figure 4 shows the evolution of the beam profile in the presence of an additional quadrupole field gradient of 1.83 T/m.

Figure 4. Evolution of the beam profile with increasing distance from the cathode with a quadrupole field gradient of 1.83 T/m.

The presented conceptual layout fulfils all necessary requirements on the IRME gun.

3.3 TUNGSTEN ELECTRON EMITTER - SIMULATION OF ELECTRON BEAM EMISSION

Based on the conceptual electron gun layout presented in the previous section, a technical design was worked out as described in the milestone report MS56 [5] and it was called tungsten electron emitter (TE²). The electrode configuration was designed to allow changing distances in order to adjust the electron current, which is mainly dependent on the electrode geometry, if necessary. The gun design was performed in several design stages, supported and evaluated by using CST-PS, until a final optimal electrode geometry was reached.

An initial design stage of the electron gun, as presented in Figure 5, was used as a model

- to evaluate the sensitivity of the extracted electron current to the cathode-to-anode distance;
- to simulate extraction under realistic conditions as expected in the real gun.

The simulation shows the possible current variation as a function of cathode-anode-distance for the planned experiments on the gun test stand. The maximum possible variation is ± 4 mm, and the design current is reached for a distance of $d_{ca}=20$ mm.

Figure 5. Initial design stage of the TE^2 electron gun (left) and simulated current variation vs. cathode-anode-distance d_{ca} (right).

Regarding simulation under realistic conditions, in the numerical model the cathode material was chosen to be tungsten and the emission model was set to thermionic emission. In reality, the cathode material has to be heated in order to provide the work function for the electrons to escape from the cathode. According to Richardson’s law, temperature drives the emission process (thermionic emission) to the point that enough charges are present and the Child-Langmuir law applies (space-charge limited emission).

Figure 6 shows the result of the extracted electron beam current as a function of the varying cathode temperature. This indicates an operating temperature of the cathode above 2500 K before space-charge limited emission is reached. Both results have to be validated with the experiments and offer valuable supporting points for a benchmarking of the simulations.

Figure 6. Extracted electron beam current vs. cathode temperature for the initial design stage.

Figure 7 shows an optimized design of the TE² electron gun. For an anode voltage of 30 kV, an electron current of 10.7 A is extracted, immersed in a homogeneous magnetic field of 0.6 T.

Figure 7. Optimized design of the TE² electron gun.

3.4 IRME GUN DESIGN PARAMETERS

Table 1 below summarizes the IRME gun design parameters. Most of the parameters, including anode voltage, grid voltage, maximum extracted beam current, and the related cathode-to-anode distance are a result of the numerical simulations. The stated value for the grid capacity, however, was measured for the electron gun prototype used in the initial design stage [5].

Table 1: Physical and technical parameters of the IRME electron gun as designed

Electron Gun Design Parameters	
Max. extracted beam current I_{\max} [A]	10.7
Max. anode voltage U_A [kV]	30
Max. grid voltage $U_{g,\max}$ [kV]	3
Max. magnetic field [T]	0.6
Cathode radius R_c [mm]	26.5
Distance cathode to anode d_{ca} [mm]	20 (variable, ± 4)
Distance cathode to grid d_{cg} [mm]	3 (variable)
Grid capacity C_g [pF]	100-125

4. Beam Transport Simulations

For the reliability of simulation results when using CST-PS, the correct choice of mesh cell type as well as number and size of the cells are decisive factors. Especially the bending sections and the beam transport in the main solenoid provide a good opportunity to validate the simulation results with analytical expressions for the drift motion of particles in toroidal fields and the ExB-rotation under the influence of the beams' space-charge. For this reason, models of subsections of the full electron lens were created in CST-PS and particle tracking simulations were performed through those.

4.1 BEAM TRANSPORT IN THE FIRST BENDING SECTION

To study curvature drift motion of the central trajectory in the toroid of the first bending section, a particle emitter was placed in the center of the solenoid with an energy of 30 keV and the electrons were tracked along the straight transport section and the bend to the exit of the toroid. In the model, a shortened main solenoid was kept to suppress the rapid decrease of the magnetic field at the exit of the toroid magnet. The maximum magnetic field in the simulation was set to 0.6 T for all magnets. Figure 8 shows the central electron trajectories along the shortened simulation set-up.

Figure 8. Central electron trajectories along the shortened simulation set-up.

In the numerical model a curvature drift of 0.725 mm (in axial direction with respect to the radius of the toroid) was obtained. This drift can be calculated by using the following analytical expression:

$$\Delta S = v_{R+\nabla B} \cdot \Delta t \text{ with } v_{R+\nabla B} = \frac{1}{RB} \left(v_{\parallel}^2 + \frac{1}{2} v_{\perp}^2 \right)$$

This evaluates to a drift of 0.73 mm for $R = \pi/4$, $B = 0.6$ T, and $(v_{\parallel}^2 + \frac{1}{2}v_{\perp}^2) = 9.15 \cdot 10^{15} \left(\frac{m}{s}\right)^2$. Obviously, the results are in very good agreement for the given simulation set-up.

4.2 BEAM TRANSPORT IN THE MAIN SOLENOID

In a next step, the ExB-rotation under the influence of the beams space-charge was validated. A simulation model comprising electron gun, homogeneous magnetic field, and a beam pipe with $r_i = 50$ mm was varied in length of the transport section (3.3 m, 4.3m and 5.3 m), while a homogeneous beam distribution of 10 A, 30 keV was tracked through the set-up. The ExB-rotation was evaluated for the different lengths and compared to the theoretical value given by:

$$\varphi = \omega \cdot t = \frac{I}{2\pi\epsilon_0 v r^2 B} \cdot t$$

Inserting $I = 10$ A, $W_b = 30$ keV, $r = 26.5$ mm, $B = 0.6$ T, and evaluating v , one obtains for the theoretical beam rotation φ_{theo} 8.4° , 11.0° , and 13.6° over transport lengths 3.3 m, 4.3 m, and 5.3 m, respectively. Meanwhile, the simulated angles φ_{sim} were 7.5° , 9.7° , and 11.8° over the same lengths.

As can be seen, the theoretical value for the beam rotation overestimates the simulated value by about 13%. The origin of this small discrepancy is not yet fully understood. However, the main solenoid of the electron lens device has a length of 3.4 m, and the corresponding difference in rotation angle of about 1° was found to be an acceptable deviation, allowing to proceed with the numerical simulations of the realistic Gaussian input distribution.

4.3 BEAM TRANSPORT THROUGH FIRST BEND AND MAIN SOLENOID

After the evaluation of the beam transport in the first bending section and the main solenoid, for given numerical settings the beam transport of the realistic Gaussian distribution through the complete set-up was simulated. Until now, only the results up to the exit of the main solenoid were validated and will be presented in this report.

Figure 9. Transport simulation in the electron lens device (top) and electron beam distributions along the beam path (bottom).

Figure 9 presents the beam transport simulation of a round, Gaussian beam distribution with $r_b = 26.5$ mm, $I = 10$ A and $U_a = 30$ kV tracked through the electron lens device considering space-charge. The colour code indicates the location of the beam distributions along the beam path: in blue is the generated electron beam distribution behind the gun, in red is the beam distribution after passing the first straight section, in purple is the beam distribution at the entrance, and in brown is the beam distribution at the exit of the main solenoid. The magnetic field shown in Figure 10 was calculated using CST EM Studio and was imported into the beam transport simulation in order to save calculation time.

Figure 10. Magnetic field in the electron lens along the beam path.

The results of the transport simulations displayed in Figure 9 show the expected behaviour of an almost conserved and slightly rotated beam distribution. On this basis, beam transport studies in order to define boundary conditions for the design of further important components of the electron lens as the collector and secondary electron suppressors may be performed.

5. Conclusion

With this report, the work of task 16.2 within the IRME work package has been completed. As mentioned above, all beam dynamics simulations necessary to verify the design of the RF modulated electron gun have been performed, resulting in a confirmation of the gun design. In particular, the compact TE² design with its electrode configuration including tungsten cathode and grid is expected to deliver the required peak current and transverse electron beam profile, which is expected to be preserved during transport into and throughout the interaction section. Thus, the gun design appears to match all requirements for integration into the electron lens for space-charge compensation in SIS18. Of course, this will have to be proven in practice during the gun tests in task 16.4.

Regarding the design of the complete electron lens, progress unfortunately did not progress as expected, such that important aspects of the design are still to be developed. This concerns, in particular, the design of the collector, the introduction of a set of correction coils for compensation of unavoidable field and alignment errors on the electron lens, and one type of correction dipoles located outside the electron lens, but also the layout of the vacuum system, support structures, and media connections. However, as stated above, the complete design of the electron lens for space-charge compensation in SIS18 is outside the scope of ARIES WP16. The development of the electron lens will nevertheless be continued outside ARIES.

6. References

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
FAIR	Facility for Anti-proton and Ion Research
GSI	Gesellschaft für Schwerionenforschung
IRME	Intense, RF Modulated Electron Beams (name of WP)
JRA	Joint Research Activity
SIS18	Synchrotron at GSI with maximum rigidity of 18 Tm
WP	Work package